

GASTROPHYLOSIS-HORSES (EQUUS FERUS CABALLUS) - HAVEN ENTOMOSIS

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Annotation: This article provides information on the biological development and parasitic characteristics of insects belonging to the family *Gasterophilidae*, which parasitize as larvae in the digestive system of animals from the *Equidae* family, specifically horses (*Equus ferus caballus*), causing myiasis. It covers the distinctive clinical signs and pathological changes of gastrofiliosis, methods for diagnosing the disease, prevention measures, and advanced approaches for control and management.

Keywords: *Gasterophilida, bioekologik, antigelmintik, abiotik va biotik omillar, ekologik, invaziyaning intensivligi hamda ekstensivligi, metemarfoz, pupa, imago, pillorik, kordial va bezli qism, gastrofilyoz, entomoz, equus ferus caballus, Gasterophilus, parazitlar patogenezi, diagnostik metodlar, terapevtik yondashuvlar, ekologik, iqlim o'zgarishining ta'siri.*

Introduction: Horses hold significant importance in agriculture and equestrian sports across all regions. [1,2,3] Currently, gastrofiliosis is considered one of the most widespread parasitic diseases among horses and remains a pressing issue for the livestock and veterinary sectors in the Republic of Uzbekistan and other countries. This disease not only affects the health of horses but also poses economic losses for their owners. [4,5,6,7]

Therefore, it is the responsibility of veterinary professionals to develop advanced technologies for studying the spread of gastrofiliosis, the biological development and parasitic characteristics of its causative agents, clinical signs, pathological changes, diagnosis, prevention, and control measures. [8,2,3,4,10,11]"

Relevance of the Topic: Climate change has been shown to alter the epizootological status of diseases, as confirmed by recent scientific research. In such conditions, developing modern diagnostic and treatment methods, as well as improving preventive measures against diseases, is crucial. [9,2,3,4]

It is evident that studying gastrofiliosis in the context of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is both scientifically and practically relevant, as it affects not

only animal health but also the material capital of the population, whose primary income comes from horse breeding in agriculture.

Therefore, research and developments addressing the spread of the disease and its prevention play a significant role in ensuring the economic stability of the horse breeding sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan. [14,13,12]

Research Objective: The aim of this study is to investigate the biological characteristics of parasites belonging to the Gasterophilidae family that cause gastrofiliosis in horses. This research will focus on the mature dipteran form of the parasite and its larval stage, which leads to the formation of myiasis through the process of metamorphosis. Additionally, the study aims to analyze the clinical and pathological processes that arise from this parasitic infection.

The research will determine the level of damage inflicted on the horse's organism by the entomosis disease, examine the stages of disease development, and seek to develop effective methods for prevention and control strategies based on advanced approaches.

Research tasks: The research tasks consist of studying the types of causative agents of gastrofiliosis and their role in the systematics of the animal kingdom, the biology of the disease, the ecological and epizootiological factors influencing the spread of the disease, the clinical signs and pathological changes, interactive diagnostic methods, the economic damage, anthelmintic resistance, and prevention and control measures.

Research Materials and Methods: Using literature sources, the study analyzed the types of causative agents of gastrofiliosis, their position within the systematics of the animal kingdom, biological development, ecological and epizootiological factors, and the levels of occurrence in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The clinical signs of the disease were studied in 15 horses, of which 3 animals that had died were examined using the "Incomplete Helminthological Dissection Method" by academician Skryabin. Samples were taken from these animals, and the indicators of invasion (degree of infestation, gastrointestinal migration, pathological changes) were studied in the "Zoology and Parasitology" educational laboratory of the Department of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacology at the Nukus branch of Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry, and Biotechnology.

Analysis of the Results: Gastrofiliosis is a disease of odd-toed ungulates (Perissodactyla) within the class of mammals (Mammalia). The mature (imago) form resembles a fly and is a dipteran insect, with larvae that obligatorily cause

myiasis in the gastrointestinal system, leading to the formation of open necrotic lesions (from the Greek “myia” - a term referring to the larvae of fly-like insects that create open necrotic foci in living internal or external organs). This disease belongs to the small family *Gastrophilidae* and the genus *Gastrophilus* (Leach), which includes the following common eukaryotic organisms: *G. intestinalis* (De Geer), *G. veterinus* (CL.), *G. haemorrhoidalis* (L.), *G. pecorum* (Fabr.), *G. inermis* (Br.), *G. nigricornis* (Low.), *G. magnicornis*, and *G. flavipes*. [18,15,16,17]

Specifically, all insects that cause damage to livestock belong to the phylum Arthropoda, subphylum Tracheata (air-breathing with tracheae), class Insecta, subclass Ectognatha (true insects with exposed mouthparts), division Pterygota, order Diptera (flies and mosquitoes), suborder Brachycera (short-horned flies), and family Oestridae (myiasis-causing parasitic flies), developing through the Holometabola (complete metamorphosis) life cycle. [11,10,9]

In the 1970s, A. Grunin wrote about the existence of 15-20 species within the genus *Gastrophilus* and their morphological identification. In this identification, based on the scientific data of Uzbek scientist M.A. Sultonov, it was established that 6 species occur in the fauna of *Gastrophilus* in Uzbekistan, and their bioecology was substantiated.

N.X. Yenileyeva, aside from studying the larvae of *Gastrophilus*, also investigated the morphology and ecology of the mature dipteran flies that develop through metamorphosis, achieving a higher degree of accuracy in distinguishing taxonomic species.

According to the data of M.A. Sultonov, Sh.A. Azimov, N.X. Yenileyeva, and B.R. Ishmirzayev, 4 species of imago and 5 species of larvae have been found in horses in the Qashqadaryo, Jizzakh, and Samarkand regions of Uzbekistan (*G. intestinalis* (De Geer), *G. veterinus* (CL.), *G. haemorrhoidalis* (L.), *G. pecorum* (Fabr.), *G. inermis* (Br.)). According to N.X. Yenileyeva, samples were found in the stomach (60.7%), the mucosa of the duodenum (39.2%), the mucosa of the rectum (0.9%), and the oral cavity (0.09%) of 419 horses examined using the complete helminthological dissection method. Of these, infection was recorded with 5 species of larvae, with the maximum intensity of invasion being 1390 specimens in the stomach and 480 specimens in the duodenum. [14,13,12]

During the active period of the imago, changes in the behavior of horses were observed, and the flight speed and distance of the insects were measured. It was proven that female dipteran gastrophil imagos can fly up to 10 kilometers in search of males for mating. [9,10,11,8,4]

Some literature states that during the mature stage, the larvae resemble flies and indicate that these imagos do not harm horses, donkeys, or mules. However, they lay their eggs by spraying them from a short distance without landing on the horse's body. In particular, this causes irritation on the lips, leading to restlessness. Due to the sounds produced by these insects' wings, the horses experience significant behavioral changes under stress.

A larva hatches from the egg placed on the horse's coat within four to five days. A single stomach bot can lay up to 700 eggs in one season. When the horse licks its skin with its tongue, the larvae that emerge from the eggs attach themselves to the horse's tongue and then travel to the stomach through the mouth. The larvae cling to the stomach wall, where they remain parasitic for a long time.

Figure 1. *Horses that died as a result of gastrofiliosis and the causative agents of gastrofiliosis.*

Sometimes, larvae are also found in the intestines of horses. The larvae in the stomach of horses hibernate and develop there, reaching a length of 12-20 millimeters. In spring or early summer, they fall to the ground with the horse's feces. On the ground, they transform into pupae. Within 25-30 days, dipteran adults emerge from them. The number of larvae in the horses' stomachs can be very high, sometimes exceeding a thousand. These larvae live parasitically in the horses' stomachs, causing significant harm by attaching to the stomach wall, leading to inflammation, severe illness, and ultimately death.

In our conducted helminthological examinations, a total of 3 horses that died with clinical signs of colitis were inspected, revealing 3,215 specimens of gastrofiliosis-causing agents. The infestation was unrelated to age, as 351 specimens were found in a 1-year-old foal. In all horses, nodules the size of walnuts were observed on the walls of the duodenum, and when cut open, they contained between 6 and 11 specimens of gastrofiliosis-causing agents.

Additionally, it was determined that the digestive system of a 4-year-old horse contained 2,305 specimens of 2-3 stage gastrofil larvae.

Figure 2. *Gastrofil larvae and their pathological effects.*

Literature indicates that the clinical signs of the disease resemble those of general malaise, changes in appetite, gastritis, gastroenterocolitis, and colitis. In our observations, in addition to these signs, clinical manifestations such as loss of appetite and salivation from the mouth due to hemorrhagic exclusion in the hard palate were observed in 9 out of 15 horses under the conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

It is recommended to find bot eggs stuck to the hairs or to use anthelmintic agents for diagnostic purposes. However, even though it is currently possible to identify 2-3 stage larvae through endoscopy, this method has not been widely applied in practice.

Among laboratory tests, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is the most reliable, but its reagents are currently not available in our republic. Additionally, a rapid immunofluorescent diagnostic method has not yet been developed. We are conducting our research to create and implement this method in practice.

Currently, various pyrethroids are being used for the prevention and control of the disease, and mechanical processing has been applied; however, the intensity and extensiveness of the disease's invasion in the Republic of Karakalpakstan remain high. Unfortunately, despite the existence of biophysical

methods to combat the disease, there has been a lack of scientific research in this area, which is a regrettable situation.

Conclusion: The larvae of the causative agents of gastrofiliosis create myiasis lesions in the digestive systems of many mammals, particularly in the stomach and duodenum of horses. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, it is necessary to seek new innovative solutions for the prevention and improvement of measures against this disease, as the current methods being implemented show low effectiveness, contributing to the high extensiveness of the disease's invasion.

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